

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL POP ART IN UZBEKISTAN.

Davlatova Shakhlokhon Abduvokhid qizi

Teacher of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506630>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the reforms being carried out in the field of culture and art in our country, the creative activities of national pop artists, the formation of national pop art, and its development.

Keywords: music, culture, national pop, instrument, group, folk performance, vocal, national music, song, performance, direction.

Introduction. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national maqom”, August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 “ On measures for innovative development of the arts”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “ On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 “ On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021”, November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 “ On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vahidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House-Museum ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [1] of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay ”, “ Shahrissabz “, “Termez ” and “ Kokand ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “ On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “ Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], 2020 “ On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Martyrs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD - 112 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [4] are becoming increasingly important.

Main part. In 1917-1950, the spiritual world of our people, which was formed on the basis of centuries-old rich musical heritage and traditions, began to be widely popularized. During this period, efforts were made to attract the general public to music amateurism and the organization of amateur circles. Professional and amateur groups began to form to promote folk songs and instrumental melodies, classical melodies and chants, which were considered musical folklore and oral traditional professional music. Adoption of the above-mentioned normative legal acts is a complex measure to raise the spiritual and educational level of the people in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to strengthen the material and technical base of cultural and art institutions, to support the industry.[5]

Along with these, Uzbek pop art in single and multi-voice stylistic directions also began to take shape. Various national vocal-instrumental ensembles, “jazz”, “symphonic-jazz” orchestras were formed, and the first generations of amateur and professional singers and musicians performing in them grew up. It should be recognized that the initial process in the formation of “pop art” is associated with the terms that express this direction of art and have become widely used in practice. For example: The term “pop” actually means building a floor or stage from boards.

At the same time, it means a stage (venue) specially built for holding concerts;

1. “Pop concert” - a concert performance composed of a set of the same or different art samples.

2. “Pop art” - a type of music, a set of multi-faceted, often light instrumental and vocal musical works.

3. “Pop music” - a type of light, colorful, diverse songs, instrumental music, composed on various themes and content, a type of musical art. [6]

4. “Pop composer” - the relative name of the creator who composes pop music.

5. “Pop singer or musician’ - the relative name of a performing artist, professional specialist.

6. Names of pop music groups: “Pop Orchestra”, “Pop-Symphonic Orchestra”, “Jazz Orchestra”, “Symphonic-Jazz Orchestra”, “Big Band”, “Pop Vocal-Instrumental Ensemble”, etc.

7. “Pop Music” (English - popmusic) - a concept of popular music widespread in Western culture.

There are its types and stylistic directions: “Rock Music”, “Hard Rock”, “Disco”, “Rap”, “Heavy”, “Blues”, etc. These terms have entered the world music world since the 50s of the 20th century. Currently, “pop singing” should be recognized as the leading direction of mass music culture. Forms and development processes of Uzbek pop art. Since the second half of the 19th century, such terms as “pop”, “pop concert”, “pop art” began to come into use among the people. This was due to the performances of the concert group GumhSari, who came to the cities of the Turkestan region on tour from Russia. [7] In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, it gradually became customary to announce the performances of the “Sing and Dance Group”, “Musical Ethnographic Ensemble” organized in Uzbekistan to the public as “concert”, “pop concert”. From this time on, terms such as “concert”, “pop concert”, “ensemble” became popular among the musicians and the people.

Tamara Khanum (1906-1987) made a great contribution to the establishment and development of modern national pop art in Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, various forms of European-style pop art have been practiced since the 1940s. They appeared in the palaces of culture of large enterprises of our republic on the initiative of Russian-speaking artists, imitating the pop orchestras that were created mainly in Moscow and Leningrad. In 1940, the “Music Hall” pop group was created in Tashkent under the leadership of M. Zholkov, and in 1942, the pop ensemble was created within the framework of the Uzbek State Philharmonic, and in 1944, the “Symphonic Jazz Orchestra” was created under the leadership of N. Zinin. The performance program of these ensembles was mainly composed of songs and instrumental music by Russian composers.

The development of modern Uzbek pop art in the 1950s-1980s. In the 50s-60s of the 20th century, concerts for fans with the participation of pop groups began to be held in our republic. In 1954, the “Pop Quartet” ensemble was created as part of the Uzbek State Philharmonic. In 1954, the “Uzbek State Pop” was created and all the groups were transferred to its structure.[8] The main goal was to develop pop music. In 1957, in connection with the VI International Festival of World Youth and Students in Moscow, the “Yoshlik” national pop ensemble was created in Tashkent. The ensemble consisted of two groups, called the “National Pop Ensemble” and the “Pop Ensemble”. Along with the leading musicians, the ensemble will include singers such as B.Zokirov, L.Zokirova, N.Zokirov, F.Sodikova, R.Nomozov, N.Eshonkhodjaev. The collective's performance program will include songs on the themes of youth, friendship, and

peace composed by composers E.Salikhov and V.Dementyev. Young artists of Uzbekistan demonstrated their art to the youth of the world and received festival diplomas. For the first time, singer Botir Zokirov will participate in the festival with his pop songs and will attract the attention of the audience. His wonderful, unique timbre, unique voice captivated all listeners and determined the career of pop singers. Then, in 1958, as a special attention was paid to pop performance in Uzbekistan, the “Uzbek State Pop Jazz Orchestra” was organized. Under the artistic direction of Sh. Ramazonov, composer Anatoly Kroll and conductor Yevgeni Zivaev began their activities.[9] The orchestra’s repertoire included “Arabic tango”, Afghan folk song “Oh, caravan leader”, “Maro bebus”, a number of Uzbek folk songs that became popular songs of the time. 0 Uzbek composers and composers paid increasing attention to the musical creativity, especially to the pop genre, and created modern songs and melodies based on folk music melodies. Composers such as M. Mirzayev, E. Salikhov, Sh. Ramazanov, Yan Frenkel, A. Nesterov, A. Malakhov, Kh. Izomov, S. Yudakov, M. Burhonov, M. Ashrafiy, Ye. Zhivayev created their works in this field. These include songs such as “O my beloved”, “Namangan’s apple”, “Heroic girls”, “Song about Tashkent”, “Tashkent sky”, “Love”, “I became a mafitun”, and works for orchestra such as “Uzbek suite”, “Spring”, “A more playful girl”, and “Lyric waltz”.

Conclusion. In the 20th century, under the influence of Western European and Russian pop art, a new direction in popular music, namely pop art, which has long been widely practiced in Uzbekistan, was born, formed, developed, became popular, and achieved creative successes.

References:

1. ABDURAUUF, A., FERUZA, M., & AMIRBEK, A. (2020). The Formation of Museums and Innovative Achievements in Uzbekistan. JournalNX, 6 (05), 14-16.
2. [http //www.lex.uz](http://www.lex.uz).
3. Mirziyoev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. - Tashkent. Uzbekistan Publishing House, 2021. 280 pages.
4. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
5. Mirhakimova, F., & Alieva, N. (2020). ARCHITECTURE OF THE ISMAILI SAMANID PERIOD. Интернаука, (18-3), 12-14.
6. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.

7. Hammidov H. History of traditional culture of traditional singing. Tashkent: Teacher; 1996. – P.52
8. Tashmatova A. History of Performing Arts - Tashkent 2017, - P. 17.
9. Utodilov A. History of execution during Uzbek public instradies. Tashkent: Teacher; 1995.- P.43.
10. Abdurakhmanov R. Navoi and his musical world.- Tashkent 2012.- P.25.

